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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning

FEMaLe

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¹ As per the project's cloud storage or per email date if applicable.

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of l Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

1. THE PROCESS: DEVELOPMENT OF DIETARY MODULE OF THE LUCY APP

The development process and timeline were the following.

2021.06 Yourcode Lab has conducted several in-person meetings with dietitians, lifestyle coaches and users of the Lucy app to analyze what items should be included in the modules and how they should appear.

2021.07 Yourcode Lab has created a wireframe to be reviewed by members from Semmelweis University as well as third-party dietitians and lifestyle coaches. The reviews proved to be positive, with some additional notes we could consider.

2021.07 Yourcode Lab has started the implementation of the modules for the Lucy Application based on the wireframes.

2021.10 Based on the meetings about Big Data during the development of D.5.2 (Questionnaire Module), Yourcode Lab has updated the wireframe design for the Dietary Module and the Lifestyle Module.

2021.10 Yourcode Lab has finalized the graphical design and the logic behind the modules.

2021.10 – 2022.03 Yourcode Lab has implemented and integrated the new modules into the Lucy application and the Lucy Backend systems.

2022.06 Yourcode Lab has sent new application version with the integrated modules to be reviewed by Apple and Google.

2022.06.09 Lucy App 2.1.0 has been approved and released in a staged release process to iOS and Android devices. It is available for the public to be used.

Please note that the development process of D5.3 (Dietary Module) and D5.4 (Lifestyle Module) were closely tied together to result in a more balanced and optimal solution.

2. THE CO-DEVELOPMENT PROCESS FOR D5.3 AND D5.4

Based on interviews with Lucy App users and pro-bono advisor, dietitian Zita Kurczewski-Tamás from London about the basic needs in relation to lifestyle and dietary factors, we have focused on sports activities and harmful habits for the Lifestyle data.

Users can track their sports activities through a clean user interface, where there are options to add details about the duration, the distance, and the intensity of the selected sport.

13 pre-created common sport types are available and a custom option, where the user can create an entry for any unique sport. We have also added alcohol, tobacco, and drug usage as an option to the application. Users can detail the entries with the rough amount used during a day. An additional extension for the lifestyle analysis is the added options 'Orgasm' and 'Masturbation' for sexual events.

To incorporate dietary data in the app, we have added two new screens: One is where the user can keep track of how much liquid they drank during a day, the other is a module where they can create food and drink 'recipes' and pick them for any of the five occasions where they can consume food or drinks (breakfast, dinner, lunch, snacks, other). Food consumption can be either tracked only by its name or by giving detailed ingredient groups.

Three groups that can be picked:

- Main ingredients (it contains meat, kind of wheat, milk, seeds, sugar, etc) with subgroups (red meat, white meat, etc).
- Quality of ingredients (bio, pre-prepared, fast-food, preservative-free, etc).
- Mode of preparation (boiled, baked, raw, etc).

For drinks, there is only one level of detail, where the main ingredients can be picked. The entries picked for these groups were hand-picked by experts from Semmelweis University, with the goal to incorporate all the items that might be relevant regarding connections to endometriosis during an analysis.

Yourcode Lab, Dr Attila Bokor, Dr Gabriella Márki, Prof Sebastiaan Meijer, Jayanth Raghothama, Zita Kurczewski-Tamás and Lucy App users co-developed and decided on the content.

3. THE CONTENT: LUCY APP DIETARY MODULE

DEBUG

 Intermenstrual day
Thu, Jul 14, 2022

-

-
Pelvic pain (4/10)

-
Confident
Happy

-

-

-
Grandma's Famous Applepie, Chicken Stew,
Milkshake, Beef Hamburger, Green tea,
Mozzarella sticks

-
1 liters - 4 glasses

-

-

-

9:02 LTE

Thu, Jul 14

18. day - 28 days long cycle

Intermenstrual day

Jun 27 Jul 24

- Symptoms
Pelvic pain (4/10)
- Mood
Confident
Happy
- Meals
Grandma's Famous Applepie, Chicken Stew,
Milkshake, Beef Hamburger, Green tea,
Mozzarella sticks
- Water
1 liters - 4 glasses

 More

